

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5345698

Time and Temporality in Archaeology

Approaching Rhythms and Reasons for Societal (Trans)formations in Prehistoric Central Europe

Current global challenges are leading to a growing interest in archaeology to contribute to the debate on resilience, vulnerability, coping capabilities and practices. Throughout the prehistory of Central Europe, social transformations can be observed that manifest themselves in changing life rhythms. The project examines what triggered such changes in the past, whether climatic, ecological, economic or socio-political challenges played a role in this process and how communities dealt with them in times of uncertainty.

Social change is a long-standing fundamental theme of prehistoric archaeology. In times of the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, global warming and increasing migration, it is worthwhile to re-examine the dynamics of similar challenges and their significance for social transformations also in the prehistoric past. In comparison to other approaches, the project questions environmental conditions and socio-political events equally with regard to their transformative potential. In particular, the aim is to investigate the temporal (ar-)rhythms and possible reasons for social changes. Different concepts such as resilience and vulnerability are addressed and qualitative and quantitative methods from the humanities and natural sciences are combined. Remains of Neolithic and Bronze Age settlements in Central Europe will be used as case studies and examined comparatively.

The project will compare high-quality sources and the high temporal resolution of data from UNESCO World Heritage sites - prehistoric pile dwellings - with those from other conservation contexts in order to develop a methodology that can be widely applied. From today's perspective, it is relevant that prehistoric archaeology has the potential to study the way in which people deal with climatic, primeval, economic, socio-political or health-related challenges over a wide range of time horizons, and thus to learn from findings on the vulnerability and resilience of past communities for the present and our future.

Key words: Prehistoric Archaeology; Social Transformations; Challenges & Uncertainty; Climate History; Mobility & Migration; Temporality; Vulnerability; Resilience; Social Practice